

Importance of Geo-Heritage and its conservation with special reference to Geo-Heritage sites of West Bengal

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Abstract

The present paper provides an overview of the importance of geo-heritage conservation, with a focus on the unique geo-heritage sites found in West Bengal, India. It highlights the significance of geo-heritage, the challenges in its conservation, and the need for a balanced approach that prioritizes preservation while allowing for sustainable development. The study emphasizes the importance of safeguarding geological wonders and natural heritage for present and future generations, considering their educational, scientific, and tourism value. It discusses the strategies and initiatives necessary to protect these sites in West Bengal while promoting responsible tourism and community engagement.

Key Words: Geo-Heritage, Conservation, West Bengal.

Introduction

The concept of geo heritage and its conservation though emerged long before but took its concrete shape in 1993 in the Malvern International Conference on Geology and Landscape. In 1991 the issue of conservation of geological heritage was first mentioned in first international symposium on the conservation of geological heritage at Digne, France.

The international literature shows that geo-heritage focused on geology and geomorphology globally, has now become important for local cultural reasons, natural resource management, land management, research, education, and tourism (Brocx 2007). **Geoheritage encompasses global, national, state-wide, and local features of geology, at all scales that are intrinsically**

important sites or culturally important sites offering information or insights into the evolution of the Earth; or into the history of science, or that can be used for research, teaching, or reference.(Brocx 2007). As geo-heritage focuses on features that are geological, the scope of which constitutes geological attributes in all forms which include different types of rock formations like igneous, metamorphic, sedimentary, stratigraphic, geochemical etc ; different types of topography like structural, Karst , desert geomorphic etc as well as paleontological , pedologic (soil formation, evolution) and hydrologic attributes.

History

The United Kingdom is considered as the birthplace of the discipline of modern Geology. Reconstruction of the Earth's history through its landform, rocks and fossils is said to begin with the early work of James Hutton (1726-1797), William Smith (1769-1839), and Charles Lyell (1797-1875). Hutton's idea that the history of rocks occurs in cycles, together with Smith's discovery of the layering of sediments across their geographic extent, are taken to mark the start of a period of geological enlightenment. Thereafter, many geologists such as Lyell, Smith, Murchison, and Sedgwick, amongst others, set in place the foundations of stratigraphy and palaeontology, (Hallam 1989). Consequently scientists appreciated of the significance of the Earth's crust and the landscape as a basis to reconstruct the Earth's development and its causal processes.

Figure 2- Rock Cycle along with layering of sediments (Smith)

Figure 2 Rock Cycle -Hutton layering

Figure 3 sedimentary rock layering

The United Kingdom is also considered to be the birthplace of geo-heritage study and systematic inventory-based geo-conservation, which is now an integral component of its education, tourism, planning and management (Anon 1990). One factor underlying this was the recognition that many geological features in the United Kingdom either are type examples that illustrate geological principles that are globally relevant (e.g., Hutton's unconformity), or that are sites where geological principles were conceived and espoused for the first time.

The significance of geo-conservation in the United Kingdom is demonstrated by the enactment of the Country Right of Way Act, which effectively placed sites of international and national importance outside the hands of ownership, and into the realm of national heritage, and is recognized as being a major achievement in protection and management of sites of geoheritage significance (Prosser & Hughes 2001). Many of the principles of geo-conservation developed in

the United Kingdom have been exported and adopted globally, particularly the inventory-based classification system and listing of sites of **geoheritage significance** (Wimbledon et al. 1995)⁵.

International conferences regarding geo heritage and geo conservation

Several international Conferences were held. Some are stated below:

1. The “Geological site conservation in Great Britain” in 1979 (Clements 1984)
2. “The use and conservation of paleontological sites” in 1987 (Crowther and Wimbledon 1988), both organized by the Geological Society of London, thus assigning to this country, from the historical point of view, the leadership of the geo-conservation movement on scientific basis.
3. It was only by the end of the twentieth century that geo-conservation was finally assumed at an international scale. Thus “First International Symposium on the Conservation of our Geological Heritage”, was held in Digne (France) in 1991 and attended by over 100 specialists from more than 30 nations (DD 1991).
4. In 1993, the Malvern Conference on Geological and Landscape Conservation was another major international scientific event, convened by the Joint Nature Conservation Committee in association with the Geological Society of London and the Geologists’ Association (O’Halloran et al. 1994).

Concept of geo- heritage

Geo- heritage has been defined in various ways. Some are :

1. “Geoheritage encompasses global, national, statewide, and local features of geology, at all scales that are intrinsically important sites **or culturally important sites** offering information or insights into the evolution of the Earth; or into the history of science, or that can be used for research, teaching, or reference” - The definition of geo-heritage is based on the Regulation of the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources of the Republic of Indonesia.
2. Geo-heritage is Geological Diversity (Geo-diversity) which has more value as a legacy because it is a record that has happened or is happening on earth. It’s of scientifically high value, rare, unique, and beautiful, so that it **can be used for research and education in the earth.**

3. Geo-heritage is a generic but descriptive term applied to sites or areas of geologic features with significant **scientific, educational, cultural, or aesthetic value**.
4. Geo-heritage refers to the geological features which are inherently or culturally significant offering insight to **Earth's evolution or history to earth science that can be used for education**.

From above definitions we have 4 (four) significant factors of which a geo site at least have one to be considered as a world heritage site

A. Scientifically and educationally significant geoheritage sites include those with geologic features and landscapes, distinctive rock or mineral types, unique or unusual fossils, or other geologic characteristics that have high scientific value

B. The sites are significant to education and research regarding different events of earth's and man's evolutionary history.

C. Culturally significant geo-heritage sites are places where geological features or landscapes played a role in cultural or historical events of the concerned area of location of the site. Mount worshipping, religious connotation of hot springs, worshipping river as goddess etc

D. Aesthetically significant geo-heritage sites include landscapes that are visually appealing because of their geologic features or processes. Many geo-heritage sites can be tourist destinations and provide local and regional economic benefits.

Outstanding Universal Value

Shall every site having those features as mentioned above will be considered as world heritage site? No They have to fulfill the criteria of having Outstanding Universal Value (OUV)

Now what is Outstanding Universal Value?

According to Paragraph 49 of the Operational Guidelines (World Heritage Conservation 1972) the concept is as follows:

“Outstanding universal value means cultural and/or natural significance which is so exceptional as to transcend national boundaries and to be of common importance for present and future generations of all humanity”.

The Convention aims at the identification, protection, conservation, presentation and transmission to future generations of cultural and natural heritage of outstanding universal value.

However Even if a property does not have outstanding universal value in respect of its geological and geomorphologic features, this may be significant in underpinning biological, cultural or landscape values and deserve recognition for this.

What features shall be there so that a geosite may be considered as having OUV ?

To be a site of outstanding universal value the site should be outstanding example representing

1. major stages of earth's history,
2. the record of life,
3. significant on-going geological processes in the development of land forms, or
4. significant geomorphic or physiographic features;

1. Some examples of Major Stages of Earth's History

- The record of crustal dynamics and tectonism, linking the genesis and development of mountains, volcanoes, plate movements, continental movement and rift valley development etc;
- Records of meteorite impacts;
- Records of glaciations in the geological past.

Sites in this category would be of outstanding universal value in exhibiting elements of earth history through rock sequences or associations

2. Records of Life

This subset includes paleontological (fossil) sites. Fossil sites throw light on stages evolution of life .

3. Significant on-going geological processes

It relates to active processes that are shaping or have shaped the Earth's surface. Properties recognized within this part of criterion viii include those that are of outstanding universal value as examples of:

- Arid & Semi Arid desert processes;
- Glaciations;
- Volcanism;
- Mass movement (terrestrial and submarine);
- Fluvial (river) and deltaic process processes;
- Coastal and marine processes.

4. Significant geomorphic or physiographic features;

Properties recognized within this part of the criterion may include those of outstanding universal value as:

- Desert landforms
- Glaciers and ice caps
- Volcanoes and volcanic systems, including those that are extinct
- Mountains
- Fluvial landforms and river valleys
- Coasts and coastal features
- Reefs, atolls and oceanic islands
- Glacial and periglacial landforms, including relict landscapes
- Caves and Karst.

Thematic approaches for selection of World Geo Heritage Sites

Besides above IUCN has developed 13 thematic criteria for selection of world Geoheritage sites which are as follows .

1. Tectonic and structural features, elements of global-scale crustal dynamics including continental drift and seafloor spreading, major crustal landforms and structural features at plate boundaries. geosynclines/anticline development and erosion; rift valley systems.
2. Volcanoes/volcanic systems Major areas and types of volcanic origin and evolution. These may include examples of major features such as the "Pacific Ring of Fire" as a global-scale expression of volcanic activity and associated crustal movements.

3. Mountain systems, major mountain zones and chains of the world.
4. Stratigraphic sites, rock sequences that provide a record of key earth history events.
5. Fossil sites-the record of life on earth represented within the fossil record (Wells, 1996).
6. Fluvial, lacustrine and deltaic systems Land systems resulting from large-scale river erosion and drainage system development, lakes, wetlands and deltas.
7. Caves and karst systems (dissolving bedrock forming cave sinkhole, sinking streams, springs etc), subterranean hydrological processes and landforms, together with their surface expressions
8. Coastal systems. The role of water at oceanic margins on large scale erosional and depositional coasts and banks.
9. Reefs, atolls and oceanic islands Geo-biological and/or volcanic features in oceanic areas or with oceanic influences.
10. Glaciers and ice caps -the significant role of ice in landform development in alpine and polar regions, including periglacial and nivation (snow) influences.
11. Ice ages global patterns of continental ice sheet expansion and recession, isostasy, sea-level changes, and associated biogeographic records.
12. Arid and semi-arid desert systems Land systems and features reflecting the dominant role of wind (eolian processes) and intermittent fluvial action as agents of landform development and landscape evolution.
13. Meteorite impact, physical evidence of meteorite impacts (astrolemes), and major changes that have resulted from them, such as extinctions of life.

Geo conservation

Geoconservation is related to this new social responsibility towards the use of Earth's resources. In spite of this general approach, geoconservation is more focused on the management of those geological elements with exceptional scientific, educational, touristic or cultural value

Digne Declaration" (DD 1991), which states: "Man and the Earth share a common heritage, of which we and our governments are but the custodians. Each and every human-being should understand that the slightest damage could lead to irreversible losses for the future. In undertaking any form of development, we should respect the singularity of this heritage".⁶ Geoconservation as an Emerging Geoscience Maria Helena Henriques & Rui Pena dos Reis & José Brilha & Teresa Mot, *Geoheritage* (2011) 3:117–128

Procedure of geo-conservation

The procedure of geo-conservation is the conservation of geosites, as basic units of the geological heritage of the Earth (Henriques 2010), by means of

1. Specific inventory,
2. Evaluation,
3. Conservation,
4. Valuing, and
5. Monitoring procedures (Brilha 2005).
6. Lastly policy formulation for conservation by the authority and strict implementation of the policy.

A geo-site is a place on the Earth's surface which represents "truly significant processes and events, time periods, features and topics" (Wimbledon 1998, p. 16) of the planet's identity.

It can be recognized through the application of the singularity principle, i.e. a place becomes a geo-site due to some specific property it detains, which is acknowledged and valued by experts, and which is singular and therefore relevant for the understanding of the Earth's history and dynamics.

World Geo Heritage Sites

- While there are 177 UNESCO Global Geoparks spread across 46 countries, India is yet to have one of its own. These global Geoparks have been selected on 13 themes as mentioned earlier.

Geoparks are conceived as “single, unified geographical areas where sites and landscapes of international geological significance are managed with a holistic concept of protection, education and sustainable development.” As of April 2022, there were 177 UGGps (Unesco Global Geo Park) in 46 countries.

A set of criteria as stated above as established by UNESCO must first be met for a geopark, as nominated by the corresponding government, to be included in the GGN(Global Geopark NetWork) :

- The existence of a management plan designed to foster socio-economic development that is sustainable (most likely to be based on agritourism and geotourism);
- Demonstrate methods for conserving and enhancing geological heritage and provide means for teaching geoscientific disciplines and broader environmental issues;
- Joint-proposals submitted by public authorities, local communities and private interests acting together, which demonstrate the best practices with respect to Earth heritage conservation and its integration into sustainable development strategies.

Indian Context

Though India till date has not been able to include any of its Geosite in Unesco Geo Park List , Geological Survey of India which is under ministry of mines and the authority concerned for declaring, maintaining and conserving the geoheritage sites has notified 34 geo sites as national geo heritage monuments.

Of late Ministry of Mines GOI has introduced a bill in the parliament ‘namely **Draft Geo-heritage Sites and Geo-relics (Preservation and Maintenance) Bill, 2022.**

The Bill is aimed at providing for the **declaration, preservation, protection and maintenance of geo-heritage sites and geo-relics** of national importance, for geological studies, education, research and awareness purposes.

In the bill **geo-heritage sites and geo-relics** are defined as follows

Geoheritage Sites:

- Geoheritage sites are “sites containing geo-relics and phenomena, stratigraphic type sections, geological structures and geomorphic landforms including caves, natural rock-sculptures of national and international interest; and includes such portion of land adjoining the site,” that may be required for their conservation or to access to such sites.
- **Georelics:**
 - A Geo-relic is defined as “**any relic or material of a geological significance or interest like sediments, rocks, minerals, meteorite or fossils**”.

Number of notified national geological heritage monuments in India

In India so far there are 34 notified National Geological Heritage Monument. GSI or the respective State governments are responsible for taking necessary measures to protect these sites. The list of the sites is appended below

Geoheritage site/National geological monument		
State	Number of assets	Geo sites
ANDHRA PRADESH	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Volcanogenic bedded Barytes, Mangampeta, Cuddapah Dist.▪ Eparchaeon Unconformity, Chittor Dist.▪ Natural Geological Arch, Tirumala Hills, Chittor Dist.▪ Erra Matti Dibbalu- the dissected and stabilized coastal red sediment mounds located between Vishakhapatnam and Bhimunipatnam.

KERALA	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Laterite near Angadipuram PWD rest house premises, Malapuram Dist.▪ Varkala Cliff Section, Thiruvananthapuram Dist.
TAMILNADU	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Fossil wood near Tiruvakkarai, South Arcot Dist.▪ National fossil wood park, Sattanur, Tiruchirapalli Dist.▪ Charnockite, St. Thomas Mount, Madras.▪ Badlands of Karai Formation with Cretaceous fossils along Karai – Kulakkalnattam Section, Perambalur District.
MAHARASHTRA	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Lonar Lake, Buldana Dist.
GUJARAT	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Sedimentary Structures – Eddy Markings, Kadan Dam, Panch Mahals Dist.
RAJASTHAN		<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Sendra Granite, Pali Dist.▪ Barr Conglomerate, Pali Dist.▪ Stromatolite Fossil Park, Jharmarkotra Rock Phosphate deposit, Udaipur Dist.▪ Gossan in Rajpura-Dariba Mineralised belt, Udaipur Dist.

	12	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Stromatolite Park near Bhojunda, Chittaurgarh Dist.▪ Akal Fossil Wood Park, Jaisalmer Dist.▪ Kishangarh Nepheline Syenite, Ajmer Dist.▪ Welded Tuff, Jodhpur Dist.▪ Jodhpur Group – Malani Igneous uite Contact, Jodhpur Dist.▪ Great Boundary Fault at Satur, Bundi Dist.▪ Ramgarh Crator Ramgarh▪ <u>Zawar</u> lead-zinc mine, <u>Zawar</u>
KARNATAKA	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Columnar Lava, St Mary Island Udupi Dist.▪ Pillow lavas near Mardihalli, Chitradurga Dist.▪ Peninsular Gneiss, Lalbagh, Bangalore▪ Pyroclastics & Pillow lavas, Kolar Gold fields, Kolar Dist.
CHATTISGARH	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Lower Permian Marine bed at Manendragarh, Surguja Dist.
HIMACHAL PRADESH	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Siwalik Fossil Park, Saketi, Sirmur dt.,

ODISHA	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Pillow Lava in Iron ore belt at Nomira, Keonjhar dist.
JHARKHAND	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Plant Fossil bearing Inter-trappean beds of Rajmahal Formation, upper Gondwana sequence around Mandro, Sahibganj dist.
NAGALAND	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Nagahill Ophiolite Site near Pungro,
SIKKIM	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Stromatolite bearing Dolomite / Limestone of Buxa Formation at Mamley, near Namchi, South district.
Total	34	

Images and significance of the sites

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
1		Volcanogenic bedded Barytes, (Barium Sulphate Deposit) Mangampeta	It is one of the largest baryte deposits of the world (98% of Indian deosit and 28% of world deosit)	Andhra Pradesh

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
2		Tirupati Eparchean Unconformity. Located in the steep natural slopes, road scars and ravines on the Tirupati-Tirumala Ghat road	The monument is a major discontinuity of stratigraphic significance that represents a sudden changes and discontinuity in the rock layers of earth's crust	Andhra Pradesh
3		Tirumala Natural Geological Arch, Tirumala Hills	It is a natural stone arch connecting two vertical hilly columns	Andhra Pradesh
4		Erra Matti Dibbalu	The dissected and stabilized coastal red sediment mounds located between Vishakhapatnam and Bheemunipatnam	Andhra Pradesh

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
5		Angadipuram Laterite, near Angadipuram PWD rest house premises	It is a rock of unique type falls outside the general classification of rock types . This exceptional formation is generally found over the parent rock types.	Kerala
6		Varkala Cliff (Vertical stone cutting due to weathering in coastal mountaneous area)	In Varkala taluk of Kerala cliffs are found adjacent to Arabian Sea .These Cenozoic sedimentary formation cliffs are unique geological features on the otherwise flat Kerala coast .	Kerala

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
7		National Fossil Wood Park, Tiruvakkarai	The park contains petrified approximately 20 million years old wood fossils scattered throught the ark having an area of 247 acres	Tamil Nadu
8		National Fossil Wood Park, Sathanur	This fossil wood park contains a tree trunk which is believed to be 100 million years old of upper cretaceous age .	Tamil Nadu
9		St. Thomas Charnockite ,St. Thomas Mount, Chennai	Charnokite rock formation is similar to granite,which has intruded into igneous rocks. The nams Charnokite came from the incident that the rocks of this lace was used in construction of tomb stone of Job Charnock, the founder of Kolkata	Tamil Nadu

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
10		Karai Badlands Formation Fossil Park	Badland topography, on either side of Alattur-Ariyalur road, spread within 40-70 km. radius marks the lower part of marine Cretaceous rocks that mainly consists of clay & sandstone of Karai Formation. Like the Grand Canyon in Colorado, US, Ariyalur is considered as a Cretaceous Park of South India by the Geo-scientist	Tamil Nadu
11		Eddy Current Marking - Sedimentary Structures-Kadana Dam	These marks are believed to result from dragging of a small limb of a larger floating log caught in a vortex or eddy current of a stream or from a movement of a pebble. The petrified marks of the eddies around the whirl balls, form spiral ribs on top of the bedding plane of a fine-grained quartz arenite bed.(sandstone)	Gujarat

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
12		Sendra Granite	It is a unique example of nature's capacity as a sculptor. It is a plutonic igneous rock of about 900 million years old. Wind and water acting over thousands of years, has sculpted the granite into marvelous structures.	Rajasthan
13		Barr Conglomerate	Barr conglomerate composed of pebbles of quartzite and rarely granite gneiss is set up in a fine grained matrix, it rests uncomfortably above the basement gneiss.	Rajasthan
14		Stromatolite Fossil Park ,Jharmar Kotra Rock Phosphate deposit	It is the largest deposit of phosphorite associated with stromatolite. it is a site which preserves early life on the earth.	Rajasthan

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
15		Gossan in Rajpura-Dariba Mineralised belt	It is rich gossan zone .Nowhere in India is found gossan with such richness. Mining of zinc is going on here for last 2000 years.	Rajasthan
16		Bhojunda Stromatolite Park	It is unique stromatolite fossils formed by blue green algae which forms a mat by attracting and bonding carbonate particles through their filaments .	Rajasthan
17		Akal Wood Fossil Park	In this wood fossil park petrified wood carries signature of the luxuriant forests in a warm and humid atmosphere bordering the sea some 180 mya.	Rajasthan

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
18		Kishangarh Nepheline Syenite	It is a pluton emplaced along the core of an antiform of metamorphites in Aravalli craton of Rajasthan. Kishangarh syenite has been dated 1590-1910 mya.	Rajasthan
19		Jodhpur Welded Tuff	The welded tuff, is a product of emanations, that spurted out from volcanic vents and were carried away by air to settle down. They are composed of glass, quartz and feldspar. On cooling, they develop joints which give rise to columns and terraces. The Malani rhyolites comprise pink, maroon, brown, purple, grey and green rhyolites separated by tuff, welded tuff and pyroclastic rocks.	Rajasthan
20		Jodhpur Group – Malani Igneous Suite Contact	This Malani igneous suite marks the last phase of volcanic activities of pre	Rajasthan

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
			Cambrian age in Indian subcontinent	
21		Great Boundary Fault at Satur	Great boundary fault is characterized by a faulted boundary between Aravallis and Vindhya. It represents a zone of disruption constituted by several parallel and oblique faults resulting in a step-like feature.	Rajasthan
22		Lonar Lake	Lonar Lake is a nearly circular crater formed due to the impact of a large meteorite on Deccan basaltic rocks of Cretaceous age.	Maharashtra

JHAM

No.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
23		Lower Permian Marine bed at Manendragarh (Marine Gondwana Fossil Park)	Marine Gondwana fossil park is a unique exposure of fossiliferous marine Permian (280-240 Ma) rocks of the Talchir formation belonging to Gondwana supergroup	Chhattisgarh
24		Columnar Basaltic Lava of Coconut Island (St. Mary Island)	Columnar Basaltic lava of Coconut Island displays the majestic array of multifaceted columns developed in the basalts of Deccan Tra. These marvellous structures called, columnar joints in geological parlance are nature's exquisite handiwork.	Karnataka

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
25		Pillow lavas near Mardihalli	Pillow lavas are formed when hot molten lava erupts under water and solidifies in the form of a roughly spherical or rounded pillow shape. The lava gets chilled so suddenly that part of the flow separates into discrete rounded bodies a few feet or less in size. The Maradihalli pillow lava is one of the best in the world and has been dated 2500 million years	Karnataka
26		Peninsular Gneiss of Lalbagh, Bangalore	The monument is over a typical exposure of peninsular gneiss- a geological expression for a complex mixture of granite rocks extensively developed throughout peninsular India. The gneiss is amongst the oldest rocks of the world and dates back to 3000 million years corresponding to re Cambrian age.	Karnataka

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
27		Pyroclastics & Pillow lavas of Kolar Gold fields, Peddapalli	Pyroclastic means broken by fire. The particles that erupted from volcanoes during explosive activities vary considerably in size and composition. All these ejected materials consolidate to form pyroclastic rocks. Pyroclastic rocks of Peddapalli are welded conglomerates of large fragments of granites, granite gneiss, basalt and banded ferruginous quartzite set in a matrix of ignimbrite.	Karnataka
28		Shivalik Fossil Park, Suketi	Shivalik Fossil Park has a collection of prehistoric vertebrate fossils and skeletons recovered from Shivalik hills. Shivalik is Asia's biggest fossil park. Fibre glass models here exhibit the six extinct animals of the area namely, Huge land tortoise, Gharial, four-horned giraffe, sabre-toothed cat, large tusked elephant and hippopotamus. These are the	Himachal Pradesh

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
			large mammals of late Pliocene and Pleistocene age and	
29		Pillow Lava in Iron ore belt at Nomira	The Nomira pillow lava of iron ore belt , Keonjhar Odisha is an exposure of well reserved pillow structures.	Odisha
30		Plant Fossil bearing Inter-trappean beds of Rajmahal Formation. upper Gondwana sequence around Mandro.	The Rajmahal hills contain plant fossils which are 68-145 my old related to Jurassic age.	Jharkhand

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
31		Nagahill Ophiolite Site	<p>Ophiolites are important records of ancient tectonic and magma evolution. They show major structural, petrographic and chemical changes during the history of plate tectonics. The Naga hills constituting the Indo Mynamarese range (IMR) in the NE State of Maniur, Nagaland, Parts of Arunachal radish and the adjoining areas of western Myanmar are known for the occurrence of ophiolitic rocks within a narrow arcuate zone along the middle of the belt.</p>	Nagaland
32		Stromatolite bearing Dolomite / Limestone of Buxa Formation at Mamley, Namchi	<p>This fossil park has beautiful algal stromatolitic structures, boulder outcrops with circular structures which are reserved as nature's amazing and exceptional creation. It provides one of the rare examples of early life in Sikkim Himalayan region.</p>	Sikkim

N o.	Image	Geo-Heritage site	Characteristics	State
33		Ramgarh crater Ramgarh	Ramgarh Crater is a meteor impact crater of 3.5 km diameter located adjacent to Ramgarh in Rajasthan.	Rajasthan
34		Zawar lead-zinc mine, Zawar	Zawar group of mines is one of the oldest zinc mines in the world	Rajasthan

Proposed West Bengal Geo Heritage Sites.

Before going to identify the geo heritage sites we shall take a look about the Physio- geographic division of West Bengal .

West Bengal is no less richer in geo-diversity given its Geographical diversity from Himalayan range in north and Bay of Bengal in south Confluence of Eastern Ghat Mountain range and Chhotonagpur Mountain range in West and extensive Fluvial network in east. Nine Physio geographical divisions are there in West Bengal which are 1. Himalayas, 2. Sub Himalayas Fans, 3. Barin Uplands, 4. Degraded Plateau in West, 5. Plateau Fringe Fans, 6. Upper Ganga Delta , 7. Reclaimed Lower Ganga Delta (Sundarban), 8. Non reclaimed Lower Ganga Delta, 9. Medinipur Coastal area. Hence it may be concluded that there will be number of geo heritage sites in west Bengal .

Fig. 4. West Bengal. Physiographic divisions. Districts shown in this and most subsequent maps are identified in the inset. (Source: Spots highlights from Survey of India. Other elevations from Shuttle Radar Topography Mission data of 2000).

Fig.4 Geographical division of West Bengal

Some of the proposed Geo heritage sites of West Bengal are listed below .

Sl No	Image	Name	Location and Charecteristics Theme	
1		Gangani Badlands .West Medinipur	Gangani located south-western corner of West Bengal is, nearly 22 m. deep natural canyon carved by the River Shilabati. Due to look and size, the place is popularly called the Grand Canyon of Bengal. It's a fascinating gorge like structure (narrow valley with steep walls) made of Lateritic	

soil formed during the Pleistocene period with a hard lateritic layer on the top. Gangani badland consists of escarpments (separates high ground and lower ground), caves, pinnacles, cliffs, pillars and butte (steep sides with flat top) -like structures formed due to weathering of laterite soil by the water channels and the wind over centuries. Depending on the various stages of geological erosion, the color of the surrounding area varies from red to yellowish-brown.

Unique
Topography
(Theme 7)

<p>2</p>		<p>Mama Bhagne Pahad (uncle nephew hill) Dubrajpur) Birbhumi</p>	<p>It is a pair of almost spherical natural boulders of granite rock, one balancing on the top of other. The balancing of the rocks is so surprising that it is a famous landmark in West Bengal, where it is known as Mama Bhagne (the maternal uncle and the nephew). The site has a number of boulders splintered across the place. Many of the boulders are balancing against each other and standing very precariously. It is in the extreme eastern part of the <u>Chota Nagpur plateau</u> where "the granite is gray and composed of glassy quartz pink, gray feldspar and black mica". Those rocks were formed during the emergence of Chota Nagpur Plateau in the extended area. Boulders were formed due to erosion of the rock by thousands of years of weathering, breakage by water flow, wind, heat as well as earthquake etc.</p>	<p>1. Balancing Boulders 2. Understanding influence of centuries of rain, heat and wind on granite (Theme 1)</p>
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<p>3</p>		<p>Wood Fossil park of Amkhoi near Bolpur Birbhumi</p>	<p>The fossil specimens found are definite proof of the presence of deciduous or evergreen forests in the area some 15-20 million years ago .. Dipterocarpaceae(shorea family) , Anacardiaceae,(Cashew family) Combretaceae (White Mangrove family) , Leguminosae(Leguminous flowering trees having pods). are some of these .Some of the genera though extinct here are till date occur in Westernghat, Myanmar and Malaysia.</p>	<p>Wooden Fossils (Theme 5)</p>
<p>4</p>		<p>Bakreshwar Hot Spring, Birbhumi</p>	<p>Hotspring is a geological feature where water is heated by geo thermal heat- heat from the earth's interior in non volcanic area .In volcanic area water comes in contact with rocks heated by magma and comes out upperground through fissures. . Bakreshwar has seven hot springs forming seven kunda(pond) . temperature</p>	<p>1.Hot Spring is Geological feature mentioned in eligibility list 2. Culturally very vibrant. (Theme 7)</p>

			<p>ranging from 80 to 200 degree farenheit each kunda having separate measre of temperature. Eg,Agni kund has 200 degree farenheit. Temperature .</p>	
5		<p>Sundarb an Delta, South 24 Pargana s</p>	<p>The largest delta in the world formed by confluence of Ganga, Brahmaputra and Meghna rivers in the bay of Bengal .Deep forest of mangrove trees ,hundreds of crisscrossing rivers and fierce animals (Royal Bengal Tiger, Crocodiles) have made the delta almost inaccessible except through river channels. It has also been assigned as biodiversity -hotspot due to its rich biota and its support to many rare,endangered and critically endangered species.</p>	<p>1.Largest Delta 2.Supporting rare and endangered species of flora and fauna (Theme 6)</p>

6		Jay Chandi hill , Purulia	<p>The hill is carrying great archeological value Geographically Joychandi Pahar is the lowest part of the Chota Nagpur Plateau. The plateau has been formed by continental uplift during the collision of the Deccan plate with the Eurasian continent, Also the hill has been formed by single . Igneous rock and the hill is now an inactive volcano. culturally it is a Neolithic habitation</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.Inactive volcano2. Made of a single igneous rock3. Neolithic habitation4. culturally vibrant (Theme 2)
7		Laljal Caves (Jhargram District) Laljal Hill Geo Heritage site Jhargram	<p>The natural cave (s) of Laljal hill It is about 200 meters high from piedment of Laljal hill which is eastern part of Chhotonagpur Plateau. It is also a great archaeological site relating to Chalcolithic age</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.Cave formation2. Chalcolithic culture (Theme 7)

8	<p><small>FIG. 4. Susunia Hill, Bankura district, an important fossil localities.</small></p>	Susunia Hill Bankura	<p>Plenty of Fossils of Vertebrates like Lion, Spotted Hyaena, Leopard, Horse, Giraffe, Indian buffalo, Spotted deer, Siwalic elephant (already extinct), Indian bison, Nilgai, Barking deer etc of late Pleistocene period(2.6 mya -11700 years BP). Human habitation dates back to Paleolithic period.</p>	<p>Availability of Plenty of Fossils illuminating about the life process of the corresponding period and the surrounding environment(Theme 5)</p>
9		Ayodha Pahar, Puruliya	<p>It is in the confluence of extended part of Chhotonagpur plateau and north eastern end of Eastern ghat mountain range comprising number of hills and hillocks. Number of water streams along with falls flow through the hill range. Geologically the hills are made of granite and gneiss . It is basically a 300-665 meter high plateau having an area of 401.4 km. The three parts of the pahar a) the almost flat plateau top with isolated peaks and hillocks, b) a steep</p>	<p>1. Education and research about tectonic movement, Earths Evolution 2. Volcanic activities (Theme 1 & 2)</p>

escarpment (slope connecting top plateau and the piedmont c) the piedmont zone at the foot hill.(gentle slope at the foothill which leads to surrounding flat area). Being an integral part of the Pre-Cambrian tract of Chhotanagpur Gneissic Complex (CGC), which was tectonically active for more than 1.6 billion years (Bhattacharya, 1990), the Ayodhya hill has witnessed a complex evolutionary history, marked by poly-phase tectonic movements, magmatic activities and metamorphism The imprints of all these events are manifest on the rock characteristics of the area

From above analysis it is proved that there are number of Geo-sites including the sites mentioned above, in West Bengal which conform to the factors required to be fulfilled for obtaining geo-heritage tag, as formulated by UNESCO.

Conclusion

From the closing decade of the last century identification and conservation of geoheritages of the world in a sustainable manner has assumed great importance. Geo assets which records various stages of earth and human evolutions through its' petrographic, palaeontologic, hydrographic, and pedologic characteristics are considered as very valuable geo heritage and these are to be protected and conserved. UNESCO has formulated several criteria for identifying Geo assets as Geo heritages. These are to be protected through the process of a) developing a management plan designed to foster socio-economic development that is sustainable (most likely to be based on agritourism and geotourism); b) Demonstrating methods for conserving and enhancing geological heritage and providing means for teaching geoscientific disciplines and broader environmental issues; and c) Joint-proposals submitted by public authorities, local communities and private interests acting together, which demonstrate the best practices concerning Earth heritage conservation and its integration into sustainable development strategies. Though India has identified 34 geo assets as Geo heritage it has to do some more work as per the guidelines of UNESCO to have the Geo heritage status of its identified assets. Similarly, authorities of West Bengal is also required to do some more work to get the national geo heritage status of its geo assets. Government institutions along with concerned non-government organisations should act in unison to achieve it.

Notes

1. Report on the expert meeting on geological and fossil sites held at 30th international geological congress (Beijing , China ,August 1996)
2. Draft Geoheritage Sites and Geo-relics (Preservation and Maintenance) Bill, 2022 ,Annexure I & II vide no. M.I-40/4/2020-Mines I , Government of India Ministry of Mines k** Dated: 15th December 2022
3. Geological World Heritage: A Global Framework -A Contribution to the Global Theme Study of World Heritage Natural Sites Prepared by Paul Dingwall, Tony Weighell and Tim Badman Protected Area Programme, IUCN September 2005
4. *UNESCO website accessed on 12.07.2023*
5. *GSI website-accessed on 14.07.2023*
6. *Wikipedia accessed on 14.07.2023*
7. *Photo credit, self and Wikipedia accessed on 14.07.2023*

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